

Notes

Spectrophotometric and conductometric study of the complex formation of cupric(II) ion and uranyl(II) ion with triflupromazine hydrochloride

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PHENOTHIAZINE derivatives have recently been used for the analytical estimation of metals through complexation. Basinska, Haleina *et al.*¹, through the formation of halomeric complex of chlorpromazine hydrochloride, estimated Hg(II), analytically and elucidated the structure of the complex by IR data. They showed that in the structure of the complex (M/L ratio 1 : 2), the bonding was through the lone pair of electrons of nitrogen atom present in dimethyl amino propyl side chain. The molecular structure of cupric chloride-chloropromazine hydrochloride was also elucidated by Huang Ping C. *et al.*². The complex (M/L ratio 1 : 1) involves the co-ordination of Cu(II) ion with both the nitrogen atoms of the ligand.

Another phenothiazine derivative triflupromazine hydrochloride has also been used as tranquilizer³. No data is available on the interaction of this compound with metal ions. The present communication reports on the interaction of Cu(II) ion and UO₂(II) ion with triflupromazine hydrochloride and the possible use of Cu(II)-complex and UO₂(II)-complex as fungicides.

Experimental

Standard solutions of cupric chloride, uranyl nitrate (BDH AnalaR) and triflupromazine hydrochloride (Doldar, Switzerland) were prepared by dissolving them in acetone. (BDH AnalaR).

Bausch and Lomb, spectronic-20, spectrophotometer was used for the measurements of absorbance. Conductance measurements were made on the conductivity bridge (W.T.W. made in Germany, type LBR/B.). Cambridge automatic recording type polarograph was used for amperometric titrations.

Absorbance and conductance measurements were made in acetone, whereas amperometric titrations were carried out in 10% acetone solution in distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Composition and stability constant of the complexes by absorbance and conductivity measurements

Ligand and metal ions on mixing gives coloured complexes. Cu(II)-complex and UO₂(II)-complex were of brown and green colour respectively. The λ_{max} for the Cu(II)-complex and UO₂(II)-complex were found by Vosburgh and Cooper's method⁴ at 480 nm and 360 nm respectively. Due to the interference of ligand in measuring the absorbance of UO₂(II)-complex the working wave length was chosen to be 440 nm, whereas, in the case of Cu(II)-complex it was kept 360 nm. Job's method of continuous variation⁵, molar ratio method⁶ and slope ratio method⁷ were used for the determination of composition. The interaction ratio in both the complexes was found to be 1 : 1.

The stability constants for Cu(II)-complex and UO₂(II)-complex were calculated from the absorbance data of molar ratio method and found to be 8.1×10^5 and 2.1×10^5 respectively and the free energy change on complex formation in both the cases were found to be -8.2 Kilo calories per mole and -7.2 Kilo calories per mole at 30° and 25° respectively.

Lambert Beer's Law has also been verified ranging from $M/200$ to $M/10000$ in the case of Cu(II)-complex and from $M/50$ to $M/5000$ in the case of UO₂(II)-complex.

Conductivity data from Job's method of continuous variation in the case of Cu(II)-complex and Job's method of continuous variation along with molar ratio method in the case of UO₂(II)-complex also confirmed the interaction ratio of 1 : 1 in both the cases, which was further confirmed by amperometric titrations using $N/10$ HCl as supporting electrolyte in both the cases.

Formula of the complex and its isolation and purification

The complexes were isolated by mixing equimolar solutions of ligand and metal ions in acetone, in the ratio of 1 : 1. The volume of the solution was doubled up by adding benzene. The mixed solution was concentrated over hot water-bath, resulting in the separation of the complexes. The complexes were further recrystallized from benzene and then dried in vacuum desiccator.

Both the isolated complexes on analysis gave the following percentages of carbon, hydrogen, chlorine and nitrogen.

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	Carbon (%)	Hydrogen (%)	Chlorine (%)
<i>Cu(II)-complex</i>			
Theoretical value	44.3	3.9	14.5
Experimental value	44.0	4.0	14.4
	Carbon (%)	Hydrogen (%)	Nitrogen (%)
<i>UO₂(II)-complex</i>			
Theoretical value	28.9	2.50	7.5
Experimental value	28.3	2.49	7.3

On calculation the molecular formula of the complexes are found to be :

IR spectra and structure of the complexes

It is reported in the literature⁸ that the ion $-R_3NH^+$ combined with X^- (where X^- is the halogen) present in the molecules of many phenothiazine drugs gives rise to a broad band generally between 2300–2500 cm^{-1} . In this case a broad band between 2420–2610 cm^{-1} was observed in the IR spectra of the ligand

corresponding to $-CH_2-N \begin{matrix} H+ \\ \diagup \\ CH_3 \\ \diagdown \\ CH_3 \end{matrix}$ group combined with Cl^- ion. But in IR spectra of both the complexes this band has totally disappeared showing thereby nitrogen of the side chain to be the site of interaction.

In IR spectra of Bulbocapnine⁹,

a sharp peak in each compound ranging from 2810–2835 cm^{-1} corresponds to the heterocyclic nitrogen attached with alkyl group. Therefore, a band at 2880 cm^{-1} in IR spectra of the ligand corresponds to the heterocyclic nitrogen attached with the alkyl group. This peak has totally disappeared in IR spectra of both the complexes showing thereby that the heterocyclic nitrogen attached with alkyl group is also the site of interaction.

On the basis of above evidence and molecular formulae already established, the following structures are proposed for both the complexes as shown below :

The above structures are similar to one observed for the cupric chloride-chloropromazine hydrochloride complex².

Fungicidal properties of the complexes

The solutions of both the complexes, cupric chloride, uranyl nitrate and ligand were prepared in 10% acetone.

A nutritive medium (2% malt and 2% Agar Agar in distilled water) for the growth of different fungi was also prepared.

Cu(II)-complex, UO₂(II)-complex, cupric chloride, uranyl nitrate and the ligand were tested against three different fungi viz., *Penicillium* sp., *Botryodiplodia* sp. and *Schizophyllum* sp.

Ligand i.e., trifupromazine hydrochloride was not able to inhibit the growth of all the above three fungi at any concentration upto 10%.

Fungi	Max. concentration of the compounds just sufficient to inhibit the complete growth of fungi or killing 100% fungi				
	Ligand %	CuCl ₂ %	UO ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ %	Cu-complex %	UO ₂ -complex %
<i>Penicillium</i> sp.	No activity	0.60	0.65	0.25	0.25
<i>Botryodiplodia</i> sp.	„	0.80	0.90	0.40	0.40
<i>Schizophyllum</i> sp.	„	1.00	1.20	0.55	0.50

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